

TRANSFORMATION OF MARKETING LOGISTICS BUSINESS PROCESSES TO WHOLESALE

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Abstract: the article describes the theoretical foundations of the concept of marketing logistics, the previously requested views on marketing logistics, and its connection with the transformation of marketing logistics practice into wholesale trade activities. Marketing logistics business processes, procurement and supply chain approaches are also presented.

Key words: marketing, logistics, marketing logistics, goods movement, supply chains, competitive advantage, delivery, purchases, flow of material resources, marketing mix.

Introduction

In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, in the direction of rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates, such goals as the development of industrial cooperation between large industries and regional enterprises, the increase in the production of local competitive products, the discovery of new strategic markets, the proportional development of regions have been set. [1]. The implementation of these goals makes the issue of organizing and managing the movement of commodity resources in the country's economy even more urgent.

As a result of interregional movement of goods, industrial production, competitiveness of local products, and industrial cooperation between regional enterprises will be established. Wholesale trade is an important link in the organization of goods movement. Business processes of wholesale trade are directly related to marketing and logistics activities. According to modern approaches, the theory of combining the functions of marketing and logistics in the goods movement system, that is, the use of marketing logistics, is being advanced. At the same time, the practice of business processes of marketing logistics is being formed.

The conditions of deep structural changes and diversification in the economy of Uzbekistan today require the use of qualitatively new approaches in the organization of material and information flows in the activities of local enterprises. Because the traditional systems of management of supply, production and sales processes cannot fully respond to changes in the market environment. Therefore, this article considers the issue of transformation of business processes of marketing logistics to wholesale trade.

Analysis of literature on the topic

In business processes, the introduction of the concept of marketing logistics in modern practice from the separate management of functions or operations of logistics is gaining momentum. In their research, M. Christopher and H. Peck justified the need to pay attention to integration processes in order to solve functional obstacles in order for enterprises to be market-oriented [9, 140 p.]. The content of marketing and logistics in business processes is

widely and sufficiently studied in modern literature. But the issues of marketing logistics in business processes have not been sufficiently studied.

M. Christopher and H. Peck were the first to propose a classification of marketing logistics business processes [9, 140 p.]. According to their classification, the business processes of marketing logistics are as follows:

- brand development (including new product development);
- development of relations with consumers (mainly, creation of loyalty of end consumers);
- customer management (creating interactions with intermediaries);
- improving relations with suppliers (strengthening mutual relations in the supply chain);
- supply chain management (including the order fulfillment process).

Along with the formation of modern concepts of marketing, in the mid-1990s, the term "marketing logistics" began to be used theoretically in scientific sources. F. Kotler (1998), a leading specialist in marketing, emphasizes that the strategic problems of distribution of goods, which are an important component and element of marketing, are related to logistics and marketing [8]. F. Kotler emphasized that the term marketing logistics is being used more and more recently, and he showed in his scientific research that it includes not only the process of movement of goods from the producer to the consumer, but also the delivery of goods and materials from suppliers to enterprises [8].

Russian scientist G.L. Bagiev (1998) included the term marketing logistics in his explanatory dictionary of marketing. G.L. Bagev interpreted marketing logistics as a method that ensures the harmony of logistics and marketing activities in the optimization of all types of flows [2].

The Polish specialist Dwiliński (1998) describes marketing logistics as a system of goods movement that guarantees the timely delivery of ordered goods in the context of logistics and marketing, using the appropriate means of transport, in the shortest time and at the lowest cost [7].

Experts Ryszard Barcik and Marcin Jakubiec (2013) define marketing logistics as a system of marketing mix (product policy, price policy, sales policy, movement policy) and logistics mix (transportation, warehousing, stock organization, packaging, order fulfillment and service). has shown in his research that it serves to satisfy the needs of customers at a high level [10].

Russian specialists A.A. Trifilova and A.N. Voronkov (2011) define marketing logistics as starting from the initial source of material flows (raw materials, spare parts, materials), planning production, physical distribution of finished products, and delivering finished products to effectively meet the needs of consumers. defines it as giving and quick management activity [11].

The role of marketing logistics in the organization of trade is given special attention in the scientific researches of A.N. Germanchuk. It was A.N. Germanchuk who showed the aspects that clearly connect marketing and logistics in sales activities and developed a model of business processes for ensuring the competitive advantage of marketing logistics [4].

As can be seen from the above analysis, marketing logistics is considered to be an important tool and a modern method of business processes related to the organization of

goods movement. The development of marketing logistics in the organization of goods movement is urgent.

Research methodology

It is known that according to the 22nd goal of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the development of industrial cooperation between large industries and regional enterprises and according to the 28th goal, the identification of new potential markets for the sale of products produced in our country is one of the main issues [1]. Defining the role of marketing and logistics in the implementation of these goals, based on a comparative analysis of marketing and logistics functions, the main views on marketing logistics were highlighted.

As a result of the synthesis of marketing and logistics functions, the ways of development of marketing logistics are substantiated. Also, the methods of monographic observation, abstract-logical thinking, and scientific observation were used to illuminate the formation of marketing logistics in procurement and supply chains.

Analysis and results

Business processes of marketing logistics mean a set of interrelated actions and operations performed in the process of managing goods, information and financial flows aimed at obtaining a result that has value for the consumer. This definition fully complies with the requirements of the process approach and takes into account the principles of PDCA (Plan-do-check-act).

Business process planning ensures that marketing and logistics plans are consistent with the overall development strategy of the enterprise.

Marketing logistics in an enterprise covers all functions of business process management. Marketing logistics is considered as a process of developing an enterprise strategy and achieving goals, taking into account the most effective use of resources in the strategic planning of enterprise activities. In the process of strategic planning, marketing logistics implements the development of a strategy and a set of tactical measures for its implementation, the creation of a sales plan between the distribution channels of goods and marketing distribution channels, and the creation of customer service standards.

Business processes for the development of marketing logistics are aimed at obtaining income in the long term, and include the establishment of long-term partnership relations with customers, business partners and competitors. Therefore, business processes of marketing logistics are a strategic asset of any enterprise seeking to strengthen its position in the market.

Customer service is one of the key factors in marketing logistics that provides competitive advantage for businesses. The process of customer service needs to improve the level of service. The closest interaction between logistics and marketing is manifested in the implementation of business processes for customer service. In this process, the following are carried out: segmenting the market for necessary services, developing a service policy, forming a range of services, increasing the level of service, analyzing the ratio of logistics costs to customer service, studying customer objections, etc.

The basis of the successful operation of the enterprise in the modern market is the management of the main processes related to the formation of value for the consumer. Elucidating the business processes of marketing logistics allows to evaluate the contribution

of each participant to the final result and the formation of the value chain. Table 1 below shows the components of marketing logistics business processes.

Table 1

Marketing logistics is the implementation of value creation for enterprises and customers in business processes

Business processes	Result	Value to the enterprise	Value to the customer
Demand management	Production planning	Increase customer loyalty	Customer satisfaction
Order management	Optimum time for a full cycle of orders	Reduce customer service time	Time value (quick to queries)
Procurement management	Forming a portfolio of orders	Ensuring quality delivery	Product value (structure, quantity and quality)
Assortment management	Forming an assortment that meets the needs of consumers	Full satisfaction of consumer demand	Product value (structure, quantity and quality)
Formation of a product distribution system	Optimal construction of the distribution channel		The value of space and time
Warehousing	Formation of an effective warehouse management system	Satisfying customer needs, reducing sales costs	Product value (quantity and quality)
Stock management	Maintaining an optimal level of stock	Optimization of warehouse logistics costs	Product value (structure, quantity and quality)
Transportation	Delivery of goods to the right place and at the right time	Reduce inventory costs, speed up product turnover	Time value
Service	High level of service quality	Reduce transportation costs	Cost of service
Selling	Pre-sale transactions	Image growth	Purchase value

According to the most basic approaches, marketing is a set of processes of demand formation, product movement and sales management in a company. Logistics solves issues related to warehousing, storage, physical distribution of finished products to consumers, supply of raw materials and other material resources to production enterprises, management of movement of goods and material resources. Factors related to the increasing problems of providing resources for production processes, optimization of the sales process in the increasingly competitive environment led to the emergence of the concept of logistics in the 60s.

Today, logistics includes management of trade operations, analysis of supplier and consumer markets, coordination of demand and supply in the market of goods and services. It can be seen that marketing issues and logistics issues are connected.

Most of the authors consider marketing and logistics to be closely related areas of independent production and economic activity.

Table 2

Comparative description of marketing and logistics research fields

No	Indicators	Marketing	Logistics
1.	Research object	The market and conjuncture of certain goods and services	Material flows moving in the market of goods and services
2.	Research subject	Optimizing market behavior for the sale of goods and services	Optimization of the material flow management process
3.	Research methods	Methods of studying demand and supply, market conditions	A systematic approach to creating material resource supply chains
4.	Final results	Recommendations on the company's production and sales strategy	System projects to meet logistics goals

Using marketing tools, the enterprise determines who its consumers are, what kind of goods they need, and how much they need. Logistics tools ensure optimal organization of flows of goods and material resources in the enterprise, delivery of finished products to consumers on time, in the required volume, to the required place. It can be seen that both of these tools in enterprise activity solve different functional tasks and in no case replace each other. Only their joint use can guarantee the efficiency of the enterprise. Enterprises can independently use both marketing and logistics in their activities.

Marketing and logistics cannot be separated from each other in the practice of organizing the movement of goods during the delivery of raw materials, spare and component parts, equipment, and finished products from production enterprises to the final consumer. Because in the system of goods movement, marketing and logistics together form the general terms and policies of the enterprise's production, supply and sales activities.

Rather than marketing and logistics performing independent functions in wholesale trade activities in supply chains, joint marketing logistics is effective due to the duplication of functions, the reduction of functions, and the transformation of functions into processes.

Table 3

Comparison of marketing logistics functions in wholesale trade with separate functions of marketing and logistics (author's approach)

Marketing	Logistics	Marketing logistics
1. Creation of a database on the company's purchasing activities	1. Analysis of the flow of goods 2. Determination of the offer of ordered goods	1. Study the needs of production enterprises 2. To study the composition and volume
2. 2. Establishing	3. Management of	

<p>partnerships with suppliers on long-term mutually beneficial terms</p> <p>3. 3. Optimizing the volume and quality of goods, price, logistics, organizational conditions for making decisions on the organization of purchases</p> <p>4. 4. Successfully updating the range of purchases and expanding their size</p> <p>5. 5. Finding viable substitutes to provide purchasing opportunities</p>	<p>relationships with suppliers by creating a base of suppliers and selecting them, coordinating their work, evaluating their functional indicators (SRM - Supplier Relationships Management)</p> <p>4. Rational organization of product storage and warehousing</p> <p>5. Implementation of ways to reduce costs of storage and purchase of products</p>	<p>of orders</p> <p>3. Selection of suppliers and evaluation of their services</p> <p>4. Minimizing the costs of storing and purchasing products</p>
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Conclusion

The end result of this business process is a high level of service, which is achieved by correctly fulfilling orders, not delaying deliveries, and delivering the right cargo to the right place at the right time.

In the conditions of digital changes, it is appropriate to implement the following in the business processes of marketing logistics in the organization of high-level service in economic systems:

creating standards of services provided to customers in supply, production and sales activities, ensuring that they meet the terms of the contract or agreement;

due to the fact that various organizational entities are involved in the process of delivering goods from the producer to the consumer, marketing logistics should be focused on the study of processes and the development of organizational mechanisms, not functions;

development of a model of marketing logistics business processes in the implementation of services in the goods distribution system, development of brokerage, wholesale and retail trade activities;

it is necessary to coordinate the management of material and information flows with the marketing strategy.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. PF-60.
2. Багиев Г.Л. Маркетинг: словарь и библиография. – СПб: Изд-во СПбГУЭФ, 1998. – 74 с.
3. BLAIK, P., 2001: Logistyka. Koncepcja zintegrowanego zarzadzania, wyd. II, PWE, Warszawa.
4. Германчук, А. Н. Специфика организации трейд-маркетинга на предприятии / А. Н. Германчук // Фундаментальные и прикладные исследования в современном мире :

матер.

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Междунар. науч.-практ. конф., 15 окт., 2019 г. – СПб. : Стратегия будущего, 2019. – С. 58-61.

5. Голиков Е.А. Маркетинг и логистика – новые инструменты хозяйствования. – М. : Издательство «Экзамен», 2006. – 220 с.

6. CIESIELSKI, M., 1999: Logistyka w strategiach firm, PWN, Poznań.

7. DWILIŃSKI, L., 1998: Wstęp do logistyki, Oficyna Wydawnicza PW, Warszawa.

8. Kotler, P. (1998) Marketing Management: Analysis, Planning, Implementation, and Control. 9th Edition, Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River.

9. Кристофер, М. Маркетинговая логистика / М. Кристофер, Х. Пек. ; пер. с англ. И. Касимова. – М. : Издательский Дом «Технологии», 2005. – 200 с.

10. Ryszard Barcik, Marcin Jakubiec (2013). Marketing logistics. <https://docplayer.net/4272544-Marketing-logistics-bielsko-biala-poland-email-rbarcik-ath-bielsko-pl-bielsko-biala-poland-email-m-jakubiec-ath-bielsko-pl.html>

11. Трифилова А.А., Воронков А.Н. Маркетинговая логистика. Учебное пособие. Нижегород. гос. архит.-строит. ун-т – Н. Новгород: ННГАСУ, 2011. – 83 с.